

NEGATIVE FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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Abstract. *In this article, one of the important issues in the education system namely negative factors affecting the quality of education and the ways to eliminate them is discussed.*

The dependence of the quality of education on the management process is shown by the example of necessary materials.

Keywords: *education negative, competence, management, activity, schools, lesson.*

In recent years, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to create a higher education system that meets the requirements of international standards. We can point to the establishment of new higher education institutions in the regions, newly constructed modern educational buildings as one of the high attention given to our youth. Classrooms are being renovated according to new modern constructions, equipped with educational equipment, educational laboratories, and modern ICT.

In his appeal, the Honorable President emphasized that "Increasing the quality of education is the only correct way of development of New Uzbekistan!". It was noted that great attention should be paid to the support of education, which is the biggest investment for new Uzbekistan, and that the status of teachers, the protection of their honor and dignity should be defined separately in the Constitution. It is clear that this in itself imposes a great responsibility on us.

Therefore, we should not forget that a quality education system creates qualified personnel, and qualified personnel builds a developed, powerful society.

We all know that the most important indicator of the activity of a higher educational institution is the quality of teaching and it remains so. But, unfortunately, it is clear that the quality of teaching is not always at a level that meets the requirements of the time, and at the same time, there are a number of problems that hinder the improvement of the quality of education in higher educational institutions and the implementation of comprehensive reforms in the republic.

The urgency of the issue is highlighted at the entrance of a university in South Africa: "It is not necessary to use atomic bombs or long-range missile weapons to destroy a country. It is enough to reduce the quality of education and allow copying (use of cheat sheets) in exams".

Therefore, the fact that the leadership of our country is paying serious attention to this issue can be seen in many decrees and decisions, including Decision No. PQ-4119 of January 16, 2019 "On additional measures to improve the control system of the quality of education", in his last lectures President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev touched on this several times and critically assessed the slowness of the ongoing work. "... But there are still no significant quality changes. The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the rectors are not paying enough attention to the issues of improving the quality of education and organizing educational activities based on the market demand".

One of the problems that negatively affects the quality of education is the fact that some professors-teachers, whose level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, professional competences

do not meet the requirements of higher education, and sometimes even secondary education, are working in higher educational institutions. Although the positive solution of this problematic issue largely depends on the responsible leaders, it is because they lack the courage to provide practical help from the scientific and methodical side, and to point out their mistakes and shortcomings in time. Therefore, it is not a secret to all of us that turning a blind eye to the solution of the problem and creating conditions for such teachers to teach has a negative effect on the quality of education.

How graduate students are employed by consumers, the problems in their pedagogical activities in schools, and the fact that they are not studied by the specialized departments of HEIs are other problems that have a negative impact on the quality of education. Although it is important for the responsible departments to conduct questionnaires and directly interact with consumers to learn the opinions of consumers in order to determine how they apply the acquired knowledge and skills in practice, as well as to make the necessary decisions and conclusions, we should consider the fact that it is not carried out in practice and will not have a positive effect on the quality of personnel being trained in the following academic years.

It is known that qualified pedagogical practice is an integral part of the work of training qualified pedagogical personnel, and it is a process that develops professional skills and qualifications of students, but in some departments, the distribution of pedagogical practice hours to intern teachers who do not have sufficient pedagogical experience, skills and qualifications has a negative effect on the quality of education and this is another indicator.

Also, due to superficial views on the organization and conduct of pedagogical practices by faculty deans, heads of departments, it has a negative effect on the acquisition of necessary knowledge and skills by students during practice.

Another important factor that has a negative impact on the quality of education is related to the management of the educational process, and the leadership of some faculties is occupied by some individuals who have low communication skills, do not have management skills, do not understand the importance of the tasks assigned to them, and do not have prestige among teachers and students.

Another negative factor is in the preparation of graduate qualifications and master's theses. Most of them, in their own way, their content and quality do not meet the requirements of the BMI Charter and the OAC. The defense process itself is just for show.

In some cases, graduate theses and master's theses are completed a day or even an hour before the actual defense without a preliminary defense, and then the preliminary defense is issued with an earlier date. The low level of introduction of new pedagogical technologies in conducting practical, seminar and laboratory training in higher educational institutions, as well as the absence of commissions for monitoring and analyzing the quality of lessons in many faculties, are of great concern to experts. Often, the fact that department heads do not analyze the lectures of professors and teachers in a scientific-methodical way, or they analyze them superficially, remains an urgent problem that requires finding a solution.

Professors-teachers should pay attention to scientific quality and quality of publications when preparing their textbooks, manuals and monographs.

We consider the introduction of a financial incentive system for teachers who have published articles in prestigious scientific journals included in Scopus and Web of Science databases, as well as monographs and textbooks, as another important step.

We are sure that it is impossible to improve the quality of education without strengthening scientific relations with foreign higher educational institutions.

It is necessary for local higher educational institutions to activate work in this regard, to develop effective mechanisms for attracting highly qualified teachers from other countries, and to organize student exchange with leading higher educational institutions of near and far abroad.

It is also necessary to organize courses in foreign languages and information and communication technologies in order to send professors and teachers to teach in foreign higher educational institutions.

There is already a need to develop a plan of measures to strengthen the participation of our teachers in foreign master's and basic doctoral studies.

In this case, we consider it useful to use the opportunities of specialists of our republic who are working or studying in higher educational institutions abroad.

We think that it is necessary to use the experience of the leading higher educational institutions of our Republic and to appoint scientific supervisors from among the professors and teachers of these higher educational institutions in organizing the preparation of talented students for writing graduation theses.

In order to increase the number of foreign students studying in the higher educational institutions of our republic, we recommend posting information about study programs taught in Russian, English and other foreign languages, as well as information about admission, living conditions, contracts, etc., on their websites. In the future, one-year Uzbek language courses should be organized for them.

In our opinion, the above-mentioned opinions allow to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions, at least partially.

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